

Pantograph-to-OHL Arc: Conducted Effects in DC Railway Supply System

G. Crotti, D. Giordano, P. Roccatò
Italian National Institute of Metrological
Research (INRIM)
Torino, Italy
d.giordano@inrim.it

A. Delle Femine, D. Gallo, C. Landi, M.
Luiso
Department of Engineering
University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”
Aversa (CE), Italy
daniele.gallo@unicampania.it

A. Mariscotti
ASTM Sagl
Chiasso, Switzerland
andrea.mariscotti@astm-e.ch

Abstract—The electrical arc occurring in the sliding contact between the supply contact line and the current collector (pantograph) of an electrical locomotive is a fast transient phenomenon able to progressively degrade the line-to-pantograph contact quality and consequently the continuity of operation. A reliable tool for the arc event detection installed on each locomotive could allow a predictive maintenance of both contact line and locomotive pantograph, with a consequent improvement of the continuity of operation of the railway system. This paper represents the first step in the development of such a monitoring system. In detail, it provides a first electrical characterization of the sliding contact and, through an electrical model, it investigates the conductive effects on the overhead contact line.

Keywords—DC railway system, Electric arc, rail transportation, pantograph–catenary, predictive maintenance

I. INTRODUCTION

In the major European electric railway systems, electric power is transferred from the supply system to the traction unit (locomotive or electro-train) through a sliding contact between the overhead contact line (OHL) and the pantograph. The latter is a servo-actuated current collector placed on the train roof that applies the right force to the contact strip against the contact line. The large power (up to about 6-8 MW) to be transferred from the OHL to the carbon blade of the pantograph through a contact section of few square millimetres makes the current collection as one of the most critical elements of the electrical railway power chain [1]. The increasing speed of commercial trains associated with the increasing power of traction units requires advanced predictive maintenance techniques to prevent degradation of the sliding contact and consequent failure of the overhead contact systems [2]. A lively research activity related to the arc modelling in power systems aims at preventing fault effects [3]. More specifically, the attention is directed to the accurate estimation of the induced effects produced by arcing in the railway systems [4], [5], to the analysis of the contact strip degradation with different material composition [6] and to the influence of some parameters affecting the arc phenomena, i.e. the power factor [7], the direct current (DC) polarity [8], etc.. The majority of such works addressed the alternating current (AC) railway supply systems, neglecting DC systems. This paper deals with such investigation through a combination of experimental and

modelling activity, on the conducted effect on the traction supply system caused by arcing phenomena in DC (3 kV). The overall objective is to identify an easy-to-use and reliable monitoring system able to quantify the quality of the OHL-pantograph contact. After a brief introduction on the effects caused by arcing events on the contact quality, the paper describes the experimental setup employed in the study of the dynamic electrical characteristics of the arc and the obtained results. A simple voltage-to-current characteristic is drawn and introduced in the complete electrical model that involves the supply system, the OHL, the train and the electric arc. Results have been analysed and compared with voltage transient events occurring at pantograph during a running test of a high-speed train.

II. THE DYNAMIC V-I ARC CHARACTERIZATION

A. Effects of pantograph arcing on railway systems

The electromagnetic field emissions are the most studied effects related to pantograph arcing, which can disturb signaling and protection devices [9]. Additionally, the arcing phenomena produce a localized very high temperature (10000 K to 13000 K) and corrosion spots of both pantograph and OHL [10] may occur. Therefore, intensive and prolonged arcing phenomena can, in the long run, damage not only the pantograph strip, but also the OHL which can, in turn, accelerate the wear of pantograph of other trains running on the same line section.

B. Brief description of the arc phenomenon

An arc is defined as an electric discharge occurring in a conductive ionized gas between two electrodes [11]. The conductive nature of the gas is provided by the plasma between the electrodes, namely a combination of positive ions and free electrons moving in a high temperature region. As depicted in 0, the ionized gas between the two electrodes can be divided in three regions: anode region, plasma column and cathode region; each region is characterized by a different voltage profile. As shown in Fig. 1, a constant gradient describes the voltage profile in the plasma column, while a non-linear voltage profile is observed for both the anode and cathode regions, where the transition occurs between solid state of the electrodes and gaseous plasma cloud [11].

For static electrodes the sum of voltage drops across the two transition regions only depends on the electrode nature.

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Fig. 1. Voltage drop behavior on the arc length

Fig. 2. Volt-Ampere characteristic of a stationary electrical arc

Fig. 3. Experimental setup and detail of contact

Fig. 4. Burning arcs on the wheel: (left) good contact, (middle) arc elongation, (right) quenching

A typical V-I characteristic of a DC arc with a specific length is shown in Fig. 2. At very low current (tens of Amps) a behavior defined by a constant arc power law can be observed; for current higher than a specific threshold the voltage level does not depend anylonger on the current value.

Interesting curves on the voltage-current (V-I) characteristic of DC low voltage arcs with static electrodes are provided by Paukert's compilation [12]. He collected data provided by 7 research institutes: a summary of figures related

TABLE I. EMPIRICAL EXPRESSION OF THE ARC VOLTAGE FOR DIFFERENT GAP VALUES

Electrode gap [mm]	V_{arc} [V]	$V_{arc}(I_{arc}=100A)$ [V]
1	$13.04 \cdot I_{arc}^{0.098}$	20.5
5	$14.13 \cdot I_{arc}^{0.211}$	37.3
10	$16.68 \cdot I_{arc}^{0.163}$	35.3
20	$20.11 \cdot I_{arc}^{0.190}$	48.2

to arc V-I characteristic with current ranging from 100 A to 100 kA is given in Table I.

For the experimental results presented here, there are different dynamic conditions with respect to Paukert's experiments by which a direct comparison is not immediate. Anyway, compatible results have been obtained, as it will be demonstrated in the following.

Setup of the arc generator

The experimental setup employed in this work was arranged at INRIM in the 90s for a research project devoted to the analysis of the electromagnetic field at high frequency emitted by the arcs generated between two sliding contacts [4] (see Fig. 3). The elements of the sliding contact, namely the OHL and pantograph, are emulated by the profile of a 60 cm diameter copper disk, coupled with the shaft of a DC motor (maximum speed $2\pi 50$ rad/s, that is 3000 rates per minute, rpm) and a real pantograph sliding element. The pantograph is kept against the copper disk edge by means of a weight that, thanks to a leverage system, provides the correct contact pressure. Moreover, a crank connecting-rod system moved by compressed air actuator, which allows an alternative horizontal translation of the pantograph, simulates the zig-zag arrangement of the actual OHL. The variation of the rotation speed of the DC motor allows the simulation of the sliding contact at different speeds of the locomotive.

The sliding contact is supplied with an almost constant DC voltage of 8 V. The electrical current flows from the positive pole of the supply system to the rotating disk through a brush system and then, through the sliding contact, to the pantograph that is connected to the negative pole of the supply system. A 156 μ H inductor (series resistance equal to 3.59 m Ω), able to partially sustain the arc arising in the sliding contact, is connected in series. A collection of pictures reproducing the sequence of the burning arc is provided in Fig. 4.

C. Experimental results

Three electrical quantities have been recorded: the current flowing in the circuit, the voltage drop across the sliding contact and the DC voltage at the power supply. These three quantities have been acquired by means an acquisition system with a sampling frequency of 10 kHz ([16]-[28]).

The acquisition system is based on a DEWETRON platform with DAQP-DMM signal conditioners, insulation level of 1.5 kV_{RMS} and bandwidth over 25 kHz; current transducers are Chauvin Arnoux PAC12 clamps, suitable for DC and AC current measurements, with a bandwidth from DC to 5 kHz.

The electrical characteristics of the arc events shown in Fig. 5 through 7 have been obtained with a speed rotation of the disk $n = 1230$ rpm corresponding to a simulated speed v of the locomotive of 139 km/h. When a good contact is present between the disk and the pantograph, the time behavior of the current in the circuit follows the typical inductor transient charging (Fig. 5).

When the arc occurs, the current time behavior follows the typical inductor transient discharge; in other words, the energy stored in the inductor is spent to keep up the arc between disk and pantograph. For the two cases, the analytical formulas are:

Fig. 5. Comparison between measured and computed arc current

Fig. 6. Arc voltage behavior for different evolution of the arc

Fig. 7. Collection of volt-ampere characteristic for random arc events

$$i(t) = \frac{E}{R} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}) \quad \text{good contact} \quad (1)$$

$$i(t) = \frac{(E - V_{arc})}{R} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}) + I_0 \cdot e^{-t/\tau} \quad \text{arc event occurring} \quad (2)$$

where τ is the system-time constant and is defined as $\tau=L/R$, being R the equivalent series resistance that takes into account the stray resistance of the inductor L and the cable connection resistance. For the arc events considered in Fig 5 an approximated arc voltage, V_{arc} , of 16.5 V can be seen as the result of sustained voltage by effect of the supply inductor. One can note that such a voltage is higher than the voltage applied by the supply system. This, as demonstrated by the good overlap between computed and measured arc current, is the contribution provided by the inductor during its discharge.

From the formula provided in Table I we can give a rough estimation of the arc length. As an example, the first arc occurrence shown in Fig. 5 ($V_{arc_exp} = 16.5$ V) has a length, of about 1 mm or less.

The onset of the arc events in the sliding contact and their characteristics (duration, length) are random. This fact produces a random current chopping with frequent interruption of the electrical circuit (Fig. 6 provides an example of such a variability). It can be seen that when there is a good contact, the current increases, for a burst of rapid arc events the current is “chopped”, the arc voltage ranges from 15 V to 25 V; longer arcs (in terms of time and/or length) produce a fast decrease of the current and consequently a fast increase of the arc voltage. The arc is broken when the energy stored in the inductor is spent to sustain the arc is finished (see Fig. 6).

Several arc events have been collected during the experimental tests. Fig. 7 shows some volt-ampere behaviors associated with arc events with random characteristics (length and duration). A direct comparison between such behavior and the qualitative behavior provided in Fig. 2 cannot be performed since the electrodes of the setup are moving. Nevertheless, it is evident that for each arc event recorded, two different volt-ampere behavior can be distinguished, one placed at higher currents in which the voltage has a lower slope and one placed at lower currents where the voltage slope is higher.

In many cases, at very low current, the voltage tends to fall down: this is the effect of arc quenching due to a limited energy available in the test circuit. In real railway systems, larger supply voltages and inductances can sustain arcs with higher transferred power.

III. ELECTRICAL MODEL OF THE RAILWAY SYSTEM

In order to study the conducted effects of the electrical arc on the supply system of the locomotive, a simplified electrical model with lumped parameters of the system is considered. It involves two electrical substations, placed at the two opposite ends of the OHL which provide the power to the supply system, i.e. the OHL and the track, and the locomotive. In the following, model details for each element are provided. To simplify the model of the electrical substation and the supply system (OHL + track), the locomotive is considered in the middle of the OHL when the electrical arc occurs. In this way, since there are two symmetric circuit branches, an equivalent circuit representing

Fig. 8. Model of the section line supplied by two substations

the parallel of the two substations and the parallel of the two-section supply system is considered.

A. Model of the electrical substations

Generally, a section line of a DC railway supply system is supplied by two electric substations (ESSs) placed at both ends as it can be seen in Fig.8. The section line length can range from 20 km to 30 km. A substation includes the AC to DC conversion and a second order low pass inductive-capacitive (LC) filter with parameter values that range from 5 mH to 6 mH and from 360 μ F to 500 μ F for the inductance and the capacitance respectively [13].

B. Model of the supply system

A more complete model of the locomotive supply system, constituted by the overhead contact line and the track should consider the distributed stray electrical parameters (inductance, capacitance and resistance) [14]. As first approach, a simplified model with lumped parameters is implemented; in detail, a T structure is selected. The values of the electrical parameters, provided by [13], are shown in Fig. 9 (square block: *two equal section lines parallel connected*).

C. Model of the locomotive

Today's electrical locomotives are complex electromechanical structures with sophisticated system for the electro-mechanical energy conversion and intelligent control systems. The aim of this activity is not addressed to a complete modeling of all the dynamics of the locomotive system; rather, the focus is on the effect of electric arc on the pantograph

voltage. For such reason, the locomotive is modeled and simulated with the input filter stage, whose output is parallel connected to a resistor that roughly describes the electro-mechanical conversion and the absorbed power. The locomotive taken into account is the high-speed Italian electro-train ETR 600. It is characterized by a maximum speed of 250 km/h and it can run under different supply system: 3 kV DC, 1.5 kV DC and 25 kV – 50 Hz and has a maximum power of 5.5 MW. The traction system is divided into four subsystems distributed along the electro-train length. At the input of such subsystem, there is a LC low voltage filter devoted to avoid the current high frequency content to be injected in the supply system. The natural resonant frequency is set to approximately to 10 Hz. Under normal operating conditions, the four LC filters are parallel connected and supplied by one pantograph. The electrical model of such arrangement is simply constituted by an equivalent LC low pass filter with rated values 11.25 mH and 20 mF for the inductance and the capacitance respectively [15]. The output is connected to a resistor whose value can range from a very high value (corresponding to a very low power absorption) to about 1 Ω that corresponds to an absorption of the maximum power (5.5 MW) with a minimum supply voltage of 2.5 kV DC.

D. Model of the arc event

The analysis of the obtained experimental data shows that, in several cases, the time behavior of the arc voltage is similar to a trapezoidal pulse. Therefore, the arc event is introduced in the electrical model of the system under test as a voltage generator that imposes the trapezoidal pulse between the OHL and the input stage of the locomotive.

IV. CONDUCTED EFFECTS OF THE ARCING PHENOMENA

A first frequency analysis of the pantograph voltage and current absorbed by the locomotive during and after an arc event has been performed. As preliminary sensitivity analysis, few parameters have been considered. Even though, as demonstrated in the previous section, the arc voltage drop between two sliding contact strongly depends on the spatial evolution (length, path, etc.) of the arc, which is random, a simple trapezoidal voltage pulse has been considered as first attempt. This shape is common for a very fast arc (2 ms – 5 ms)

Fig. 9. Sketch of the entire electrical model used to estimate the conducted effects produced by an arc.

Fig. 10. Computed time behavior of voltage at the pantograph and absorbed current behavior when an arc event occurs at 0.05 s with an amplitude pulse of 50 V and a duration of 5 ms. A zoom on the arc voltage around the arc occurrence is shown.

Fig. 11. Spectrum of the current absorbed by the train a) and the voltage downstream of the pantograph b) during the arc event (observation time $T_w = 3$ s).

that corresponds to short arc length. The analysis has been carried out by varying the duration and intensity of voltage drop and the DC current absorbed by the train in steady state conditions. The frequency analysis has been performed with two different observation time window: $T_{w1} = 3$ s and $T_{w2} = 0.8$ s. Two different values for the arc voltage amplitude: 25 V and 50 V and 5 different time duration values, ranging from 1 ms and 5 ms, have been considered in the analysis.

An example of the transitory conducted effect produced by the arc phenomena is shown in Fig. 10 for both the voltage computed downstream of the pantograph and current absorbed by the train. Such behavior has been obtained by applying a pulse voltage, simulating the arc, with amplitude of 50 V and duration of 5 ms. The frequency content of both voltage and current has been computed with an observation time window of 0.8 s and results are shown in Fig. 11. The frequency content of the current is concentrated around 10 Hz, at the natural resonance frequency of the loco on-board filter; other components, but smaller, are located around 128 Hz, the resonance frequency of the substation low pass filter including line effects. A different situation is found for the voltage frequency content: two narrow spikes at 128 Hz and 4.5 kHz can be observed: the latter corresponds to the resonance frequency of the traction line. Table I and Table II provide the voltage magnitude corresponding to the two mentioned frequency components when an arc voltage peak of 25 V and 50 V is selected for the trapezoidal pulse simulating the arc.

TABLE II. CONDUCTED EFFECT FOR ARC VOLTAGE AMPLITUDE OF 25 V

Pulse duration (ms)	Frequency (Hz)	Amplitude (mV)	
		$T_{w1} = 3$ s	$T_{w1} = 0.8$ s
1	128	71	249
	4560	30	106
2	128	124	436
	4560	<u>472</u>	<u>1540</u>
3	128	157	550
	4560	208	710
5	128	146	500
	4560	367	1200

TABLE III. CONDUCTED EFFECT FOR ARC VOLTAGE AMPLITUDE OF 50 V

Pulse duration (ms)	Frequency (Hz)	Amplitude (mV)	
		$T_{w1} = 3$ s	$T_{w1} = 0.8$ s
1	128	142	500
	4560	62	210
2	128	248	872
	4560	<u>945</u>	<u>3000</u>
3	128	314	1100
	4560	416	1400
5	128	293	1000
	4560	735	2500

Each table provides the voltage magnitude for the chosen pulse duration and for the two observation time windows. Contrarily to what it is expected, the higher impact of the arc event on the voltage at the pantograph is not detected when higher amplitude and/or duration of the pulse simulating arc is applied. In fact, there is an anomalous result for pulse duration of 2 ms. With this test condition, for both pulse amplitudes, the highest frequency (4.56 kHz) component value has been recorded (the results are underlined). Further investigation will be performed to better understand this phenomenon. In addition, it can be stated that a shorter observation time window can emphasize arc effects on the train supply and very fast and small arc events can be more easily detected. A first analysis of the model reliability has been carried out thanks to some measurements of the voltage and current at the pantograph made available by Trenitalia S.p.A., the Italian National railway company. The voltage recorded close to the pantograph of a high speed electro-train (ETR 600) during a performance test highlights a dumped oscillation (see Fig. 12 a) which frequency is around 3.3 kHz. A deviation of 36% from the computed oscillation frequency is found. Even though the discrepancy seems to be relevant, the two result can be considered coherent. In fact, the different position of the train along the section line in the simulation and in the real case associated with the differences of the overhead line stray parameters can justify the discrepancies.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper, through a laboratory characterization of the arc produced by sliding contacts and an approximated model of the railway system, shows the conducted effects produced by the arc events on the train supply voltage and absorbed current. The two observed quantities (pantograph voltage and absorbed current) show different frequency spectra when an arc occurs.

Fig. 12. a) time behavior of a voltage recorded at pantograph for the ETR 600 class electro-train. b) frequency spectrum of the same voltage before (window 1) and during (window 2) the transient oscillation. (waveforms provided by Trenitalia)

The current has a frequency content concentrated at low frequency (around 10 Hz), while the voltage shows two predominant frequency components, at 128 Hz and 4.6 kHz. Due to many mechanical transients and the train driver activity, characterized by spectral components around 10 Hz, the current absorbed by the train is not a good choice as a detector quantity.

This investigation, by identifying the observation quantities and quantifying their peculiarities, constitutes the first step in the development of a measuring system for the detection of arcing events between overhead lines and train pantograph for power quality and predictive maintenance purposes. To support the theoretical results shown in this paper, an on-site measurement campaign will be carried out, for a more accurate characterization of the train supply voltage associated with arc events and its detection, based on pantograph detachment.

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